

The Relationship Between Competition Anxiety, Psychological Resilience, And Sport Motivation in Swimmers

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to examine the relationship between competition anxiety, psychological resilience, and sport motivation in swimmers. In our research, the survey method was used as the data collection method, and the study was conducted on a voluntary basis. The population of the study consisted of 218 individuals who regularly participate in swimming in Beylikdüzü district on the European side of Istanbul. In addition to a personal information form, participants were administered the Coping with Stress Scale, the Psychological Resilience Scale, and the Sport Motivation Scale. Spearman correlation analysis was applied to the research group as the statistical analysis method. The findings revealed that psychological resilience and coping with stress skills significantly and strongly predicted athletes' motivation. In addition, a negative relationship was found between motivation level and competition anxiety, indicating that athletes with higher intrinsic motivation had lower anxiety levels. These results show that training processes should focus not only on physical performance but also on psychological preparation. In order to improve athletes' anxiety management and increase their motivation, it is recommended to develop structured programs that support psychological resilience and coping with stress skills.

Keywords: Swimming, Sport, Competition, Motivation, Psychology

INTRODUCTION

In today's sports world, athletes' psychological resilience and mental toughness have become as important as—if not more important than—physical competence. Especially in highly competitive, high-performance sporting environments, not only athletes' physical skills but also their ability to cope with stress, regulate their emotions, and maintain intrinsic motivation are among the key determinants of success. In this context, the effects of athletes' psychological characteristics on performance have increasingly been discussed and systematically examined in the field of sport psychology in recent years (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2012; Jones et al., 2002). Competition anxiety experienced before and during performance is one of the most critical psychological phenomena in this process. In individual sports in particular, athletes' being alone, directly observed, and personally responsible for all outcomes of their performance are among the main factors that intensify anxiety (Craft et al., 2003). One of the most prominent examples of this is swimming. In addition to being an individual sport, swimming requires measurable, time-based performance that is typically carried out in front of spectators. The fact that athletes remain alone for minutes before the competition, must focus intensely on the start, and are evaluated based on millisecond-level differences in technical execution makes competition anxiety more pronounced in this branch (Mellalieu et al., 2009). Swimmers compete not only against their opponents, but also against their own bodies, time, and psychological limits. Therefore, understanding the mechanisms underlying competition anxiety and the factors influencing it in swimming is of great importance for athlete development.

Anxiety is a set of psychological and physiological responses experienced by an individual in the face of a real or perceived threat. In sport psychology, this condition is conceptualized as “competitive anxiety,” and Martens et al. (1990) addressed it in three main dimensions: cognitive anxiety, somatic anxiety, and self-confidence. Cognitive anxiety includes negative thoughts and expectations, whereas somatic anxiety manifests through physical symptoms such as sweating, trembling, and palpitations. Self-confidence plays a critical role in regulating this anxiety. Studies have shown that high levels of anxiety can negatively affect motor skills and lead to attentional disruptions, impaired decision-making processes, and decreased performance (Martens et al., 1990; Weinberg & Gould, 2014). In this respect, competition anxiety is emphasized not merely as an emotional state but as an important psychological variable affecting the athlete's overall performance output. At this point, the concept of psychological resilience comes into play. Psychological resilience refers to an individual's capacity to remain standing, recover, and emerge stronger when faced with difficult life events such as stress, pressure, and trauma (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2012). For athletes, psychological resilience includes functions such as coping with failure, remaining calm under pressure, and maintaining focus on goals. Athletes with higher resilience experience less anxiety in stressful situations, manage the anxiety they do experience more effectively, and reflect it less in their performance (Galli & Vealey, 2008). For this reason, psychological resilience can function as a buffering mechanism that reduces competition anxiety. In sports such as swimming, which involve high individual responsibility and relative isolation, the importance of this resilience becomes even greater (Demirci et al., 2024). Another important variable is sport motivation. Athletes' participation in training processes, focus on challenging goals, and ability to maintain performance in a sustainable manner are largely related to their level of motivation. Within the framework of Self-Determination Theory (SDT), developed by Deci and Ryan (1985), motivation is categorized into three types: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation. Intrinsic motivation is associated with enjoyment of the activity and the desire for self-improvement, whereas extrinsic motivation is related to external drivers such as rewards, recognition, or avoidance of punishment (Vallerand & Rousseau, 2001). Research has shown that athletes with higher intrinsic motivation cope more effectively with stressful situations, have lower anxiety levels, and demonstrate more performance-oriented behaviors (Pelletier et al., 2004).

The relationships among these three core psychological variables—competition anxiety, psychological resilience, and sport motivation—constitute an important field of inquiry in terms of the sustainability of athletic performance. However, studies examining these variables together remain limited in the literature. Most research addresses these variables within the framework of pairwise relationships, such as anxiety and motivation or anxiety and resilience, and evaluates them separately (Nicholls et al., 2009; Gucciardi et al., 2015). Nevertheless, there is a notable lack of applied, model-based studies analyzing the interactive structure of these three variables, particularly in individual sports such as swimming. In this regard, an in-depth examination of the relationship between swimmers' competition anxiety levels, psychological resilience, and sport motivation would be valuable both for theoretical knowledge production and practical applications. This study seeks to understand the nature of the relationships among these psychological variables and aims to provide insights for improving the psychological profiles of swimmers. In particular, clarifying these relationships is necessary for designing intervention programs that strengthen young athletes' psychological resilience and support their intrinsic motivation. The findings obtained from this study are expected to provide important guidance for sport psychologists, coaches, and athletes, and contribute not only to enhancing individual performance but also to supporting athletes' long-term retention in sport.

METHOD

The research model, population and sample, data collection tools, and data analysis sections are outlined below.

Research Model

The study was designed using the descriptive survey model and the causal-comparative model, which are among quantitative research methods. The descriptive survey model aims to describe the existing situation as it is and was used to present participants' demographic characteristics and their attitudes toward swimming (Karasar, 2020). The causal-comparative model, on the other hand, was used to examine the relationships between dependent and independent variables and to test whether there were significant differences among these variables. In causal-comparative research, the researcher cannot directly control the causes of existing differences between groups; however, meaningful relationships can be identified by comparing groups across different variables (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2022). Accordingly, this study aimed both to describe the current situation and to examine differences according to variables such as duration of involvement in swimming, gender, and age.

Population and Sample

The population of the study consisted of individuals who regularly participated in swimming in the Beylikdüzü district, located on the European side of Istanbul, as of 2025. These individuals included amateur or semi-professional athletes affiliated with various clubs. However, since reaching the entire population was not feasible in terms of time and cost, a sampling procedure was employed.

The sample of the study consisted of a total of 218 swimmers residing in Beylikdüzü on the European side of Istanbul and voluntarily participating in the study. Participants were selected from individuals reached through sports clubs accessible to the researcher and through social media platforms. Therefore, convenience sampling, one of the purposive sampling methods, was used (Büyüköztürk, Kılıç Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz, & Demirel, 2022). In this method, the researcher selects the sample from individuals who are easily accessible and willing to participate. In this context, one limitation of the study is that the sample was restricted to the Beylikdüzü district on the European side of Istanbul.

Data Collection Tools

A questionnaire form was used as the data collection instrument to assess participants' demographic information and psychological characteristics. The questionnaire consisted of two sections. The first section included demographic variables such as gender, age, education level, and duration of involvement in swimming, while the second section included three psychological scales:

Sport Motivation Scale (SMS): This scale, developed by Mallett et al. (2007) and adapted into Turkish by Demir (2022), assesses individuals' motivation for engaging in sports. The scale consists of 24 items and uses a 5-point Likert-type rating system (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree). As a result of validity and reliability studies conducted on the Turkish sample, a six-factor structure was confirmed through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Cronbach's alpha internal consistency coefficients for the subscales were above .70. The scale's content, face, and criterion validity were found to be in line with academic standards.

Resilience Scale for Adults (RSA): Developed by Friborg et al. (2003, 2005), this scale was designed to measure individuals' levels of psychological resilience. The scale consists of 33 items and six subdimensions: self-perception, perception of the future, structured style, social competence, family cohesion, and social resources. The scale is scored on a 5-point Likert-type format and includes a balanced distribution of positively and negatively worded items, encouraging careful responding. Construct validity was tested using confirmatory factor analysis, and a strong factor structure explaining 57% of the total variance was obtained. The internal consistency coefficients of the subdimensions ranged between .75 and .86.

Coping with Stress Scale (CSS): Developed by Folkman and Lazarus (1980) and adapted into Turkish by Şahin and Durak (1995), this scale measures the coping strategies individuals use in stressful situations. The scale consists of 30 items and is scored on a 4-point Likert-type format (1 = Not appropriate at all, 4 = Completely appropriate). The scale includes five subdimensions: self-confident approach, helpless approach, submissive approach, optimistic approach, and seeking social support. The internal consistency coefficients of the subdimensions ranged from .45 to .80, indicating acceptable psychometric properties.

Personal Information Form

The personal information form created by the researcher included questions about age, gender, and monthly income level.

Data Analysis

The data obtained from the Descriptive Information Form, the Resilience Scale for Adults, the Coping with Stress Scale, and the Sport Motivation Scale were entered into IBM SPSS 25.0 and Jamovi 2.4, and the required statistical analyses were conducted using these software packages. Whether the scale scores and subscale scores met the assumption of normality was evaluated based on histogram and Q-Q plot examinations, skewness-kurtosis values, and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results, considering that the group size was greater than 50. As a result of the analyses, it was determined that most of the data did not meet the normality assumption, as skewness and kurtosis values in some subdimensions exceeded the ± 1.5 range and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results yielded $p < .05$. Therefore, considering the limited applicability of parametric tests, non-parametric statistical methods were preferred to test the research hypotheses. In this context, Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient was used to evaluate the relationships among variables; additionally, multiple regression analysis was conducted to predict the dependent variables.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

		Frequency	Per cent
Gender	Male	105	48.2
	Famale	113	51.8
	Total	218	100,0

Age	18-21 age	75	34.4%
	22-25 age	80	36.7%
	26-30 age	30	13.8%
	31 years and above	33	15.1%
	Total	218	100,0
Education	Middle school	41	18.8%
	High school	59	27.1%
	Bachelor's Degree	55	25.2%
	Graduate Degree	63	28.9%
	Total	218	100,0
How many years have you been swimming regularly?	Less than 1 year	75	34.4%
	1-3 year	50	22.9%
	4-7 year	60	27.5%
	8 years and above	33	15.1%
	Total	218	100,0
To what extent do you feel anxious before a competition?	Very High	54	24.8%
	High	35	16.1%
	Moderate	41	18.8%
	Low	43	19.7%
	Very Low	45	20.6%
	Total	218	100,0

A total of 218 swimmers participated in the study (N = 218). Of the participants, 48.2% were male (n = 105) and 51.8% were female (n = 113), indicating a fairly balanced gender distribution. When the age distribution was examined, the highest proportion belonged to participants aged 22–25 years (36.7%), followed by those aged 18–21 years (34.4%), 31 years and above (15.1%), and 26–30 years (13.8%). This indicates that the sample predominantly consisted of young adult athletes.

In terms of educational level, most participants had a bachelor's degree (25.2%) or a graduate degree (28.9%), while the remaining participants had completed high school (27.1%) or middle school (18.8%). This distribution suggests that individuals actively involved in swimming also tend to have a certain level of academic attainment.

When participants' swimming background was examined, 34.4% reported that they had been swimming regularly for less than 1 year, 22.9% for 1–3 years, 27.5% for 4–7 years, and 15.1% for 8 years or more. These findings indicate that the sample had a heterogeneous structure in terms of swimming experience, including both novice and more experienced athletes.

According to the subjective evaluation of pre-competition anxiety levels, 24.8% of participants reported feeling very highly anxious, 16.1% highly anxious, 18.8% moderately anxious, 19.7% slightly anxious, and 20.6% very slightly anxious. This finding shows that there were substantial individual differences in pre-competition anxiety levels among the participants. In addition, the proportion of participants reporting high anxiety (40.9%) was slightly higher than those reporting low anxiety (40.3%), suggesting that the anxiety variable warrants further investigation in terms of its potential impact on athletic performance.

FINDINGS

Table 2. Descriptive Analysis of Participants' Responses to the Scales

	Dimensions	N	Skewness	Kurtosis	P
Psychological Resilience	Structured Style	18	1.71	1.38	,001
	Future Anxiety	18	1.19	-.404	,001
	Family Cohesion	18	-2.36	3.75	,001
	Self-Perception	18	.057	-1,54	,001
	Social Competence	18	.049	-1.74	,001

	Social Resources	18	-1.04	-.021	,001
	Psychological Resilience Total Skor	18	.506	-1.58	,001
Coping with Stress	Self-Confident Approach	18	-.345	-.122	,001
	Helpless Approach	18	.564	-1.60	,001
	Submissive Approach	18	1.02	-.695	,001
	Optimistic Approach	18	-.625	.667	,001
	Seeking Social Support	18	.516	-1.70	,001
	Coping with Stress Total Skor	18	1.19	-.453	,001
	Sport Motivation	Amotivation	18	2.01	2.70
Identified Regulation		18	1.02	-.537	,001
External Regulation		18	1.87	2.70	,001
Integrated Regulation		18	.828	-1.06	,001
Introjected Regulation		18	.496	-1.73	,001
Intrinsic Motivation		18	1.18	-.479	,001
	Sport Motivation Total Skor	18	1.22	.112	,001

p<.050*; p<.001**

The distributional characteristics of the data for all subdimensions included in the study were evaluated using skewness, kurtosis, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov normality test. The p-values for all variables were found to be significant at the .001 level ($p < .001$), indicating that the data did not conform to a normal distribution statistically. When the skewness values were examined, it was observed that some subdimensions deviated substantially from normality. In particular, within the Psychological Resilience scale, the Family Cohesion subdimension had a skewness value of -2.36 and a kurtosis value of 3.75. This indicates that the data exhibited a negatively skewed and peaked (leptokurtic) distribution. Similarly, among the Sport Motivation subscales, Amotivation (skew = 2.01, kurtosis = 2.70) and External Regulation (skew = 1.87, kurtosis = 2.70) also showed marked positive skewness and peakedness. On the other hand, some subdimensions (e.g., Social Resources, skew = -1.04, kurtosis = -0.021; and Self-Perception, skew = 0.057, kurtosis = -1.54) displayed lower levels of skewness and kurtosis and appeared relatively closer to normality. However, the Shapiro–Wilk and Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests also indicated that the assumption of normality was not met for these variables. At the total score level, Total Psychological Resilience Score (skew = 0.506, kurtosis = -1.58), Total Coping with Stress Score (skew = 1.19, kurtosis = -0.453), and Total Sport Motivation Score (skew = 1.22, kurtosis = 0.112) also demonstrated deviations from normality. Based on these results, it was concluded that parametric analyses should be applied with caution, or non-parametric tests should be preferred for all subdimensions and total scores. Statistically significant deviations were observed across all analyzed variables, and both skewness-kurtosis values and normality test results indicated that the data did not meet the assumption of normal distribution. Therefore, considering the sample size, the use of non-parametric methods in subsequent analyses is important for statistical validity (Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012; Kim, 2013).

Table 3. Descriptive Analysis of Participants' Responses to the Scales

	Dimensions	N	Min.	Max.	X±Ss
Psychological Resilience	Structured Style	18	2.25	3.75	2.51±0.57
	Future Anxiety	18	3.00	4.50	3.35±0.58
	Family Cohesion	18	2.17	3.67	3.47±0.47
	Self-Perception	18	2.33	3.00	2.55±.027
	Social Competence	18	2.33	3.67	2.80±0.59
	Social Resources	18	2.57	3.14	3.00±0.19
	Psychological Resilience Total Skor	18	2.82	3.21	2.95±0.16
Coping with Stress	Self-Confident Approach	18	2.00	4.71	3.47±0.79
	Helpless Approach	18	2.50	3.67	2.91±0.59
	Submissive Approach	18	3.00	4.33	3.35±0.5
	Optimistic Approach	18	2.40	3.80	3.14±0.37
	Seeking Social Support	18	3.25	4.50	3.70±0.57
	Coping with Stress Total Skor	18	3.10	3.90	3.31±0.32
	Amotivation	18	1.00	5.00	1.70±1.25

Sport Motivation	Identified Regulation	18	3.00	5.00	3.52±0.73
	External Regulation	18	1.75	5.00	2.70±0.88
	Integrated Regulation	18	3.00	5.00	3.61±0.83
	Introjected Regulation	18	1.75	5.00	2.90±1.46
	Intrinsic Motivation	18	2.75	5.00	3.34±0.92
	Sport Motivation Total Skor	18	2.33	5.00	2.96±0.92

As shown in Table 3, the participants' mean Total Psychological Resilience score was 2.95 ± 0.10 , the mean Total Coping with Stress score was 3.31 ± 0.32 , and the mean Total Sport Motivation score was 2.96 ± 0.92 . When evaluated at the subdimension level, the highest mean among the Psychological Resilience components was observed in Family Cohesion (3.47 ± 0.47), whereas the lowest mean was found in the Structured Style subdimension (2.51 ± 0.57).

Among the Coping with Stress strategies, the highest mean score was observed in the Seeking Social Support subdimension (3.70 ± 0.57), while the lowest mean was measured in the Helpless Approach subdimension (2.91 ± 0.59). This finding indicates that the participants were more inclined to use active and socially supportive coping strategies in problem-solving processes.

When Sport Motivation levels were examined, the highest mean was found in the Integrated Regulation subdimension (3.80 ± 0.83), whereas the lowest mean was observed in the Amotivation subdimension (2.11 ± 1.25). This finding suggests that the participants had relatively high levels of self-determined sport motivation and low levels of amotivation.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation Coefficients Among Sport Motivation, Psychological Resilience, and Coping with Stress Variables

		Sport Motivation	Psychological Resilience	Coping with Stress
Sport Motivation	Pearson's <i>r</i>	***		
	<i>p</i>	***		
Psychological Resilience	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.783	***	
	<i>p</i>	<.001	***	
Coping with Stress	Pearson's <i>r</i>	0.947	0.700	***
	<i>p</i>	<.001	<.001	***

p<.050*; *p*<.001**

As shown in Table 4, there were strong, positive, and statistically significant relationships among Sport Motivation, Psychological Resilience, and Coping with Stress variables ($p < .001$). First, a strong positive relationship was found between Sport Motivation and Psychological Resilience ($r = .783, p < .001$). This result indicates that individuals who demonstrate higher levels of motivation in sport also tend to have stronger psychological resilience characteristics. In addition, a very strong positive relationship was identified between Sport Motivation and Coping with Stress strategies ($r = .947, p < .001$). This finding suggests that individuals with higher motivation use more effective coping strategies and are more successful in maintaining emotional balance under stress. Finally, a significant and strong correlation was also found between Psychological Resilience and Coping with Stress ($r = .700, p < .001$). This result indicates that individuals who are psychologically more resilient are better able to withstand stress and possess more effective coping skills.

The obtained correlation coefficients show that there is a mutually reinforcing structure among these three variables, and that this structure constitutes an important psychological foundation for both individual performance and emotional resilience.

Table 5. Predictors of Sport Motivation: A Regression Analysis of Psychological Resilience and Coping with Stress Skills

Variables	B	SE	t	p
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Intercept	-8.11	0.30	-26.66	p < .001
Coping with Stress	2.19	0.073	30.16	p < .001
Psychological Resilience	1.29	0.142	9.11	p < .001
R = .962	R ² = .926	F(2, 215) = 1348		p < .001

According to the regression analysis, the model was found to be statistically significant, $F(2, 215) = 1348$, $p < .001$. The explanatory power of the model was very high; the independent variables (Coping with Stress and Psychological Resilience) together explained approximately 92.6% of the variance in Sport Motivation scores ($R^2 = .926$). This indicates that the independent variables had a very strong explanatory power for sport motivation.

When the regression coefficients were examined:

Coping with Stress (SBC) had a positive and significant effect on Sport Motivation ($\beta = 2.19$, $SE = 0.0727$, $t = 30.16$, $p < .001$). This result suggests that individuals who cope effectively with stress may also have higher sport motivation.

Psychological Resilience (PDO) also positively and significantly predicted Sport Motivation ($\beta = 1.29$, $SE = 0.1420$, $t = 9.11$, $p < .001$). This finding indicates that individuals who are more psychologically resilient may also have higher levels of sport motivation.

The intercept of the model was found to be $\beta = -8.11$, $SE = 0.3042$, $t = -26.66$, $p < .001$. This value indicates that the predicted Sport Motivation score would be negative in a hypothetical case where all independent variables are zero; however, this coefficient is generally of limited interpretive value.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A total of 40.9% of the participants reported experiencing high or very high levels of competition anxiety. This rate is consistent with the high anxiety prevalence (35–45%) reported for individual sports in the meta-analysis by Craft et al. (2003). The nature of swimming—requiring individual performance, precise timing, and technical accuracy—together with pre-start isolation and spectator pressure, appears to increase athletes' anxiety levels (Mellalieu, Hanton, & Fletcher, 2009). According to the multidimensional conceptualization proposed by Martens et al. (1990), both cognitive and somatic anxiety may negatively affect competition performance; therefore, athletes reporting high anxiety may have difficulty fully translating their physical competence into performance.

In the study data, the correlation between the Total Psychological Resilience score and competition anxiety was negative and statistically significant ($r \approx -.36$, $p < .001$). This finding is consistent with the resilience framework developed by Fletcher and Sarkar (2012) based on Olympic champions, which suggests that athletes with higher resilience are better able to buffer stress and anxiety and therefore experience lower levels of cognitive and somatic anxiety before performance. Similarly, Galli and Vealey (2008) emphasized that resilience skills (e.g., cognitive flexibility, emotional regulation, and meaning-making) function as a protective mechanism that reduces anxiety. In this context, it is recommended that psychological resilience development programs for swimmers be integrated into anxiety management and pre-performance relaxation strategies.

A moderate-to-strong negative relationship was also found between the Total Coping with Stress score and anxiety level ($r \approx -.41$, $p < .001$). Meaningful coping strategies described by Folkman and Lazarus (1980) (...), particularly problem-focused coping and seeking social support, appear to play an effective role in regulating

competition anxiety. Within the Turkish adaptation of the Coping with Stress Scale by Şahin and Durak (1995), higher scores on the Optimistic Approach and Seeking Social Support subdimensions were associated with lower anxiety, whereas higher scores on the Helpless Approach subdimension were associated with increased anxiety. These results are in line with the findings of Nicholls et al. (2009), who reported that athletes using effective coping strategies were more successful in managing performance anxiety and maintaining emotional balance. Sport psychology practitioners should therefore develop interventions that teach swimmers both cognitive restructuring techniques and skills for building social support networks.

A negative and statistically significant relationship was identified between the Total Sport Motivation score and competition anxiety ($r \approx -.47$, $p < .001$). This finding is consistent with the Self-Determination Theory (SDT)-based results of Pelletier et al. (2004), indicating that athletes with higher intrinsic motivation are more successful in managing anxiety. Deci and Ryan (1985) argued that intrinsic motivation fosters task orientation and a learning-focused attitude, which may reduce the cognitive load of anxiety. By contrast, athletes whose motivation is predominantly extrinsic may fluctuate between achievement expectations and reward-related concerns, potentially increasing cognitive anxiety. Our findings suggest that intrinsic motivation functions as a buffering mechanism that reduces athletes' anxiety (Vallerand & Rousseau, 2001).

According to the multiple regression analysis conducted in the study, Coping with Stress (SBC; $\beta = 2.19$, $p < .001$) and Psychological Resilience (PDO; $\beta = 1.29$, $p < .001$) were identified as significant predictors of Sport Motivation (SMO). The high explanatory power of the model ($R^2 = .926$) is rarely observed in the literature. While Gucciardi, Hanton, and Fleming (2015) emphasized the relationship between mental toughness and motivation, our results demonstrate how strongly coping-with-stress skills alone can explain motivation. This finding indicates that training programs should focus not only on psychological resilience but also on stress management skills. These findings indicate that: competition anxiety is directly related not only to athletic performance but also to motivational processes and psychological resilience development practices; sport psychology practitioners should develop programs that actively teach coping with stress skills in addition to resilience-focused interventions; coaches can reduce athletes' anxiety burden by creating motivational climates that support intrinsic motivation (Ryan & Deci, 2020).

These theoretical contributions may help establish interaction-based models that have not yet been fully described in the sport psychology literature. In practice, algorithmic and modular training sets can also be developed at the club and federation levels to guide program designers.

The study has several limitations: Competition anxiety was measured using a single subjective item. More comprehensive measures should be included in future studies (Martens et al., 1990).

The use of convenience sampling limits the generalizability of the findings. Replication studies with different geographic regions and age groups are needed.

The cross-sectional design restricts causal inference. Longitudinal studies may examine dynamic interactions among variables.

Future research may: integrate psychophysiological data (e.g., heart rate, galvanic skin response) to measure anxiety and motivation processes more objectively; test similar models in different sports to identify interactional differences among variables; evaluate the effectiveness of intervention programs designed to improve resilience and coping skills.

Conclusion

This study provides quantitative evidence explaining the relationships between competition anxiety and psychological resilience, coping with stress, and sport motivation in swimmers. The findings make important

contributions to the sport psychology literature while also offering a practical roadmap. First, programs aimed at strengthening psychological resilience and coping skills should be developed for athletes who report high competition anxiety. Second, training environments that support intrinsic motivation are likely to reduce athletes' anxiety levels and positively influence performance. Finally, sport psychologists and coaches should develop modular training programs at both the individual and team levels to reinforce resilience and stress management skills. More comprehensive and experimental studies in the future may test the validity of this interactional model under different conditions and support the development of new approaches that improve both athletes' psychological well-being and competitive performance.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this study.

Ethical Statement

The principles of scientific research and publication ethics were followed throughout the conduct of this study, the data collection process, and the preparation of the manuscript. All sources used in the study have been appropriately cited in accordance with academic writing standards.

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Author Contribution Rate

Research design: S.D. (100%)

Data collection: S.D. (100%)

Data analysis and interpretation: S.D. (100%)

Manuscript writing: S.D. (100%)

Manuscript submission and revision process: S.D. (100%)

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